

Literature Review on International Strategic and Operational Decision-Making Mechanisms in Businesses

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Abstract

The first step in conducting a systematic literature review is to decide the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the studies, and the second step is to decide the quality level of the studies to be included in the review (Briner & Walshe, 2015). Using the following three key inclusion criteria, the identified preliminary list of articles was narrowed down to theoretical, conceptual, or empirical papers of particular interest that focus on uncertainty in international decision-making. This was conducted by applying the following criteria. To begin with, for an article to be evaluated, it must first be a peer-reviewed study published in a scientific journal between 1912 and 2017, and should also be ranked as level 3, level 4 (ABS, 2015). Earlier reviews recommend relying on peer-reviewed academic journals that have the most impact in the IB field (Hennart & Slangen , 2015) and serve as guardians of quality research (eg, Vaara & Whittington, 2012). These definitions are

particularly effective in research on uncertainty (e.g., Miller, 1992). They do this by supplying clear information about various definitions and/or measures of uncertainty. Articles to be included in the review should clearly focus on the impact of uncertainty (or synonyms) on the international strategic and operational decisions taken by multinational companies (for example, decisions about foreigners directly). Investment and related strategies, entry mode choices, and foreign partner and market selection (e.g., product development, personnel, inter-firm trade) resulted in fewer articles by reading the titles of the articles individually and removing duplicates from the list. The excluded articles focused their attention on alternative units of analysis (such as country) rather than multinational companies (MNCs). The third and final inclusion criterion was that the articles either explored the impact of uncertainty on the international decision-making processes of MNCs or explored the types of uncertainty management strategies put in place. This criterion is used to explore how the identified uncertainties affect the decision-making processes of MNCs when running in an uncertain environment and how MNCs respond to these uncertainties. Each of the articles supplies a precise explanation of uncertainty (or one of its synonyms), focusing on the characteristics of this concept (ie, environmental, industry, or firm uncertainties). In addition, these publications do not include any measurement of the degree of uncertainty. The review did not include experimental publications that did not supply a clear definition of uncertainty dimensions and/or measurements. In conclusion, it should be noted that the scope of this systematic review is limited as it does not include research published in book form, in other journals, or in languages other than English.

Keywords: *Keywords: Business, International Strategic and Operational Decision, Investment and Related Strategies, Management Strategies*

1. Introduction

Discussion and analysis of several articles The method of Denyer and Tranfield 's (2009) systematic review was adhered to throughout the entire analysis, which took place in three main stages. The nature of the analysis was descriptive, as the theoretical frameworks and empirical methodologies of the publications selected for analysis were different. In the first step of this

process, articles were evaluated for the amount and type of uncertainties addressed (i.e., the expressions used and defined in the article) to create a complete list of the various uncertainties that stood out.

both Miller (1992) and Simangunsong, Hendry and Stevenson (2012) were used to group defined approaches that refer to the two main methods of uncertainty management (reduction and coping), and there are eight approaches to uncertainty management. falls into these two categories. In the final stage of the analysis, the dimensions of uncertainty and uncertainty management approaches found were analyzed in terms of the ability of MNCs to add value to our understanding of international decision-making (i.e., "how about identified dimensions of uncertainty and uncertainty management approaches?" to improve our understanding of MNCs in international decision making. ?').

This was done to decide whether the dimensions of uncertainty and uncertainty management approaches found could add value to our understanding of international decision-making by MNCs. The research uncovered several contradictions and disagreements held by IB scholars about the impact of uncertainties on MNCs' decision-making processes, as well as the reasons for MNCs' decisions about their uncertainty management strategies.

2. An Integrated Framework for Managing Uncertainty Based on Different Management Strategies

The aim of this research is to propose an integrated framework for managing uncertainty based on classifications of various aspects of uncertainty and different management strategies. The inconsistency in earlier work on the implementation of ideas is the primary driving force for the use of an integrated framework. Therefore, it became difficult to draw conclusions based on what we already know about the role that uncertainty plays in the decision-making process of MNCs.

framework includes updated uncertainty dimensions based on Miller's (1992) definition of diverse types of unpredictability (2012), as well as adjusted uncertainty management strategies based on work by Miller (1992) and Simangunsong et al. The framework was changed in response to the

emerging evidence from the systematic literature review. As a result of these changes, the framework now includes both modified and new types of uncertainty, as well as innovative approaches to uncertainty management. These are all in Miller (1992) and Simangunsong et al. they did not expect it to be included in their original framework (2012). In the reviewed literature , the five characteristics of individual decision makers, which are considered to have an impact on the individual decision makers' feelings of uncertainty or on the choice of uncertainty management approach, are not based on any pre-existing framework, but rather emerge from them. These five characteristics of individual decision makers were considered to have an impact either on the individual decision makers' feelings of uncertainty or on the choice of uncertainty management approach.

3. Various Degrees of Uncertainty, Both Outside and Inside the Organization

The contextual aspect is represented by varying degrees of uncertainty both outside and inside the organization. Multinational companies respond to these uncertainties in many ways, depending on the situation. Individual effects are related to how the qualifications of individual decision makers affect both their feelings of uncertainty and MNC 's methods for uncertainty management. In this part of the work, we describe the interconnections that exist between the various components of the framework in relation to the proposed research agenda. This study uses the uncertainty categorization developed by Miller (1992) to promote better uniformity in the concept of uncertainty dimensions in future research. This includes thirteen distinct aspects of uncertainty classified as belonging to three diverse types of uncertainty: environmental, industry and company uncertainties. The framework developed by Miller (1992) was chosen because it is comprehensive and is often used in IB research (for example, Ahsan and Musteen (2011); Clark, Li , and Shepherd (2017); Erramilli and D'Souza (1995)). ; Oetzel and Oh (2014)). It neither relied on a comprehensive review of the existing research group nor was it empirically investigated in its thoroughly unmodified form. This can be considered a possible negative. However, Miller's (1992) classification serves as the basis for this work and the following additions and changes are made to it:

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- *To begin with, a more in-depth analysis of the IB literature led to the addition of one dimension to the list. categories in which the industry falls into uncertainty (i.e., technological),*
- *Second, the firm category of uncertainties was changed (i.e., the debt and credit dimensions of uncertainty were removed, and earlier experience added), the social and product dimensions of uncertainty were renamed to cultural and demand uncertainties, and the natural dimension of uncertainty was renamed to discontinuous uncertainty.*

On the other hand, the inconsistent application and measurement of ideas made it difficult to draw conclusions based on prior knowledge of the role played by uncertainty. While most scholars agree that multinational companies use a variety of strategies to manage uncertainty in their decision-making processes, what exactly is meant by uncertainty and how it is measured varies from research to study. These differences include studies that use different uncertainty concepts to capture the same uncertainty dimension; studies using concepts of the same name for diverse types of uncertainty ; and studies using different measures for the same type of uncertainty.

Extensive review of the handling of decision-making uncertainty found in the IB literature was one of the main aims of this piece of research. This is true regardless of the type of uncertainty considered. Specifically, studies have explored environmental uncertainty in political (U2) (eg, Agarwal & Ramaswami , 1992; Delios & Henisz , 2003a; Kobrin , 1979), economic (U1) (eg, Brouters & Dikova , 2010; Prater , Biehl & Smith, 2001; Song , 2015) and government (U3) (e.g., Akhter & Robles , 2006; Chiao).

Other studies examine environmental uncertainty in terms of cultural uncertainty (U4) that arises between home and home (for example, Cho & Padmanabhan , 2005; Dow, Cuypers & Ertug , 2016). (“Policy Uncertainty and the Sequence of Entry by Japanese ... - ResearchGate”) Consequently, these studies focus on the informal aspect of a country's environment. For example, Cho & Padmanabhan (2005) and Dow, Cuypers , & Ertuğ (2016) are two examples. The importance of the impact of industry uncertainty has been highlighted in several other studies. For example, Elango and Sambharya (20 04) discovered that competition and demand uncertainty have

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a major impact on the choices MNCs make in their approach to entry. Gray (1994) puts more emphasis on the technical uncertainty that arises in the decision-making process about the entry methods of MNCs. It is generally accepted that previous experience of a MNC has an impact on the identification and perception of various other dimensions of uncertainty (Brouthers , 1995), entry mode selection decisions (Brouthers , Brouthers , and Werner, 2008) or location decisions.

Among the various dimensions of uncertainty that fall under the category of firm uncertainty, MNC 's earlier experience has attracted the most research attention and is widely recognized as having such an impact (Delios & Henisz , 2003b). Studies investigating the impact of uncertainty dimensions within a category (for example, environmental or industry uncertainty) are the most common type of research conducted in the IB area. This is even though IB researchers are aware of the existence of more than one uncertainty category. Of the 114 studies reviewed, 32 investigated the impact of environmental dimensions of uncertainty (18 studies focused on operational decisions, seven studies focused on entry mode, four studies focused on location decisions, two studies focused on divestiture, and one study focused on an international joint venture property decision), and 14 The study explores the impact of industry dimensions of uncertainty (nine studies on operational decisions, three studies on entry mode, one study on location, and one study on decision speed).

There is a steady shift towards integration of uncertainty in a variety of areas , including but not limited to:

Twenty studies examine the simultaneous impact of environmental and industrial aspects of uncertainty on each other. However, empirical research on several types of uncertainty has typically been conducted across multiple studies rather than within a single study. Most conceptual papers are articles that consider the effects of two or three forms of uncertainty.

Uncertainty management frameworks developed by Miller (1992) and Simangunsong et al. (2012) was chosen as a starting point. More specifically , this review considers two approaches to managing uncertainty proposed by Simangunsong et al. (2012).

These approaches include reducing uncertainty (what Miller calls "financial risk" management) and dealing with uncertainty (what Miller calls "strategic management"). The vulnerability of a multinational company to various uncertainties is reduced by reducing the uncertainty that does so without the company needing to change its business plan (Miller, 1992). Reduced Uncertainty is a Natural Primary Motivator and Basic Needs that Guide the Behavior of Multinational Corporations (Beckman , Haunschild , & Phillips, 2004; Mullin & Hogg , 1998). On the other hand, coping with uncertainty has an impact on MNC 's exposure to a wide spectrum of uncertainty , forcing the MNC to adjust its strategy in certain situations (Miller, 1992).

This article adopts the terminology of Simangunsong et al.(2012) because the IB literature reviewed mostly refers to uncertainty management in terms of mitigation and coping rather than financial and strategic risk management. Although the two concepts are the same in both frameworks, this article adopts the Simangunsong et alterminology , summarizing the research done as opposed to the two ways of managing uncertainty, and these are presented as follows:

Three strategies for reducing uncertainty and five ways to deal with it. There are methods outlined in the IB literature for overcoming the problem of managing uncertainty .

4. Reduction for Uncertainty

Analysis of selected articles made it possible to find three strategies to reduce uncertainty:

information gathering (R1), initiative-taking collaboration or collaboration (R2) and networking (R3). The concepts of information gathering (R1), and networking (R3) are entirely original to the literature reviewed, and neither framework refers to them.

Collaboration (R2) was discovered because of literature research and is also included in the list of ways to reduce uncertainty presented by Simangunsong et al. (2012). Since the words collaboration and collaboration are used interchangeably throughout the research under review, this study combines the two concepts. Information gathering (R1) is a strategy for reducing uncertainty used by multinational companies (MNCs) to avoid decisions considered risky and act only when the information gathered is considered sufficient to achieve analytical comprehensiveness (e.g.,

Brouthers et al., 2008). ; Ji & Dimitratos , 2013). According to the findings of the studies, information gathering is a method to reduce uncertainty in which multinational companies (MNCs) research the external environment and collect key data without the involvement of other partners. Information gathering is the most used strategy to reduce uncertainty and is largely used to limit demand, competition and cultural uncertainties. This is because information gathering is the most common approach used (for example, Cadogan , Cui , & Li , 2003; Grunert , Trondsen , Campos , & Young, 2010; Keats & Hitt , 1988; Petersen, Pedersen, & Lyles , 2008; Rhee & Cheng, 2002).). Another technique for improving the predictability of outdoor conditions is to engage in initiative-taking collaboration or collaboration, which we will refer to as R2. Information exchange is an integral part of any kind of cooperation or collaboration (Simangunsong et al., 2012). The IB literature discusses cooperation and collaboration in the form of vertical integration and contractual agreements that MNCs have with their local partners for collaborative planning and forecasting to mitigate the impact of external uncertainties . (“Uncertainty in decision-making: A review of the international business ...”)

Vertical integration refers to the process of combining two or more businesses into a single entity (Brouthers et al., 2008; Slangen and van Tulder , 2009). According to research, environmental uncertainties and factors contributing to industrial uncertainties such as demand and competitiveness can be mitigated by collaboration and collaboration with local partners (Brouthers et al., 2008; Slangen & van Tulder , 2009). Through increased networking, uncertainty can be significantly reduced (R3). According to the findings of IB studies, reducing uncertainty through networking (R3) occurs when data is collected through strengthening social relationships and existing networks (Luo , 2003; Ottesen & Grnhaug , 2004). This occurs when MNC collects data through social relations and strengthening existing networks. According to Ottesen and Grnhaug (2004), initiative-taking collaboration and collaboration (R2) can be a part of networking (R3) and takes place within larger networks.

According to research published in the IB field, the primary goal of networking is to reduce three types of industry risk:

Input, demand and competition (e.g., Beckman et al . , 2004; Luo , 2003).

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The reviewed IB literature points to five strategies that are consistent with Miller's five strategies for dealing with uncertainty. These five strategies are:

These strategies include avoidance (A), flexibility (C1), imitation (C2), reactive cooperation/cooperation (C3) and control (C4) (C5). Flexibility⁶ (C1), collaboration/cooperation⁷ (C3) and avoidance⁸ (C5) are some of the other ways mentioned by Simangunsong et al. (2012).

Diversification and operational adaptability are two aspects of flexibility (C1) that can be seen. Diversification through its involvement in various markets or diversity of product offering enables the multinational company to better manage the risks associated with the industry (for example, Chiao et al., 2010; Liu, Shah, and Babakus, 2012). Changing the organizational structure or approach depending on the situation is one method of achieving operational alignment. For example, when there is too much unpredictability within the company, many multinational companies will switch from FDI to non-equity models (Lee & Makhija, 2009a). Some multinational companies choose to be copycat as a risk management strategy (C2). MNCs assume that their competitors' activities involve learning to help them avoid mistakes made by early movers while mimicking the tactics of one of their competitors (Gaba, Pan, & Ungson, 2002). However, a leader in the industry will be able to expect the reactions of the competitors because the responses of the competitors will be nothing but imitations of the leader's own strategic moves (Miller, 1992). In the context of decision-making at the international level, political, administrative, cultural and demand-related insecurities can be managed by imitating the actions of competitors (e.g., Gaba et al., 2002). The literature review revealed that the reactive collaboration/collaboration (C3) strategy is the most widely used method for dealing with environmental and industry uncertainties (e.g., Brouthers (1995); Brouthers and Brouthers (2003); Dickson and Weaver (1997); López-Duarte and Vidal-Suárez (2010); Morschett, Schramm-Klein and Swoboda (2010); Tseng and Lee (2010)). MNCs tend to choose methods that transfer uncertainty and risk to their partners when the level of uncertainty in the environment and industry increases (Brouthers, 1995).

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On the other hand, when there is a significant opportunity for growth, collaboration and collaboration lose some of its value (J. Li and Li , 2010). It is possible for multinational companies to decide to control uncertainty unilaterally (C4) instead of passively accepting uncertainty. The use of control entry methods is common among knowledge-intensive multinational companies (Sanchez - Peinado & Pla-Barber , 2006). Vertical integration with suppliers is often used to have better control over supply and demand variability (e.g. , Akhter & Robles , 2006). Horizontal integration , such as mergers and acquisitions, is used to reduce competitive risks, particularly in the transitional phase of an economy in which a multinational corporation (MNC) runs (Burgers & Padgett , 2009; Mayrhofer , 2004).

When the amount of environmental and industrial uncertainty faced by a MNC reaches an intolerable level, the company will begin to avoid uncertainty (C5). MNCs delay acting as a method of total uncertainty avoidance until the value of an investment opportunity has been accurately estimated. This allows them to avoid making hasty decisions (eg, Dowell & Killaly , 2009; Whitelock & Jobber , 2004).

The literature review revealed that the theoretical background of the research and the specific decision makers within the MNC are two factors that influence the choice of a particular uncertainty management technique by the MNC. . In terms of the theoretical framework that underpins the research, for example, studies using a real options theory perspective describe using an uncertainty management method known as the reactive collaboration/collaboration (C3) approach (e.g., Brouthers et al . , 2008). Cuyper & Martin, 2010; Li & Li , 2010). According to this idea, multinational companies should consider environmental uncertainty not only because it is a problem in decision making, but also because it presents an opportunity overall (e.g. , Li & Li , 2010).

On the other hand, a transaction cost perspective reports the use of control (C4) (e.g., Akhter & Robles , 2006; Tseng & Lee, 2010), while the internationalization perspective reports that both information gathering (R1) (R1) (e.g., Petersen et al. , 2008; Rhee & Cheng, 2002;) and reactive collaboration/collaboration (C3) approaches to uncertainty management.

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Both perspectives report on the increasing use of approaches (e.g., Sanchez - Peinado & Pla-Barber , 2006). This is especially true when MNC behavior differs from that predicted by theoretical models (for example, in studies by Gray , 1994 ,; Richards & Yang, 2007). Therefore, this article examines individual decision makers and the characteristics that define them to understand the impact of these individuals on the uncertainty management method chosen by their MNCs . The inductive method was used to conduct a systematic review of the literature on individual-level characteristics of decision makers (ie, no underlying classification was used).

As a result, the following features appeared after the analysis:

- *earlier experience with decision making,*
- *tolerance for ambiguity ,*
- *individualistic /collectivist orientation,*
- *hierarchical position in the organization and*
- *decision making. -orientation*

Earlier decision-making experience or lack thereof can have a significant impact on an individual's feeling of uncertainty (for example, Makhija & Stewart , 2002; Whitelock & Jobber , 2004). To be more specific, the degree of perceived uncertainty was higher, and the likelihood of a third party being involved in the management of international operations increased in direct proportion to the amount of managerial experience an individual manager had (Brouters , 1995). The research reviewed finds two of Hofstede's (1980) cultural dimensions applied at the individual level to show how the characteristics of individual decision makers shape their feelings of uncertainty . These two cultural dimensions are uncertainty avoidance and individualistic/collectivist orientation, more commonly known as tolerance for uncertainty in international decision-making research. Both cultural dimensions have been applied to show how the characteristics of individual decision makers shape their feelings of uncertainty. The term "uncertainty tolerance", abbreviated as "I2", refers to the tendency of certain decision makers to view uncertain conditions as proper (Eroğlu, 1992). Individuals with a limited tolerance for uncertainty tend to stop information processing early and are resistant to retrieving added information, the obvious difference between the two

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groups. Individuals who are more willing to tolerate uncertainty are more open to receiving information from the outside world (Makhija & Stewart , 2002; Yasai-Ardekani , 1986).

According to research conducted by IB, decision makers with a weak tolerance for uncertainty will distribute resources to overseas markets only if environmental and industry uncertainties are reduced below the maximum degree of risk, they are willing to accept. However, if perceived environmental and sectoral uncertainty levels continue to increase over time, it is still unknown how decision-makers who dislike uncertainty will act (Petersen et al., 2008). According to the logic of maximum tolerable risk, the solution is to withdraw from the international market (Johanson and Vahlne , 1977). However, added empirical research is needed to understand the actual behavior of individual decision makers who tolerate varying degrees of uncertainty. It has been shown that the individualist/collectivist orientation of the managers affects the way they perceive the uncertainties that MNCs face. Managers with an individualistic orientation value independence and self-sufficiency, and highly value social justice and equality. They also highly value self-management (Dickson & Weaver , 1997). In the bona fide business world, these managers are less influenced by their feelings of the state of the environment and are more cautious in seeking partnerships in international markets (Dickson & Weaver , 1997).

Managers with a collectivist perspective emphasize the value of belonging to a group, highly value cooperation among group members, and expect help from the group. These managers have a more optimistic view of partnerships and are more influenced by their feeling of the unpredictability of the environment (Dickson & Weaver , 1997; Makhija & Stewart , 2002). One's place in the organizational hierarchy (I4), which encompasses organizational tasks, experiences, beliefs, and ideologies, has been proven to have an impact on how one perceives uncertainty (Yasai-Ardekani , 1986). Managers higher up in the organizational hierarchy have greater access to environmental scanning and information processing than lower-level managers. For this reason, it is easier for senior managers to obtain information and, as a result, reduce uncertainty. In addition, one's place in the social hierarchy affects how he interprets his environment (Sonnenfeld , 1981as Yasai-Ardekani , 1986). The mindset that decision makers adopt during the information processing stage is called decision-making orientation (I5) (Makhija & Stewart , 2002).

In terms of how they respond to environmental uncertainties, there is a significant gap between entrepreneurial and innovation-oriented decision-makers and conservatism -oriented decision-makers in their decision-making processes. (Dickson and Weaver , 1997). Entrepreneurial decision makers are characterized by increased risk taking and are less likely to view the situation as dangerous. This is because entrepreneurial decision makers tend to see challenges as opportunities stronger (Hodgkinson , Hughes, & Arshad , 2016). The international entrepreneurship literature works on the assumption that decision makers are risk takers who focus on possibilities rather than threats presented by overseas markets.

5. Initiative-taking and Risk-Seeking Decision Makers

On the other hand, decision makers who are initiative-taking and risk seeking can transfer such risks to unknown but potentially lucrative future economic prospects (Johanson & Vahlne , 1977; Petersen et al., 2008). Considering the findings of this extensive literature analysis, it is reasonable to draw three conclusions about the main shortcomings of earlier IB-related research. These limitations include:

- (i) *inconsistency in conceptualizing and measuring uncertainty.*
- (ii) *lack of variation in uncertainty dimensions within a single study; and*
- (iii) *individual decision makers.*

After first providing a brief description of each of these limitations, the study offers some specific suggestions for how future research might address these limitations, along with an explanation of why they are problematic for the development of knowledge. The first identified constraint towards more consistent choices in conceptualizing and measuring uncertainty is the inconsistency in understanding and measuring uncertainty, which is the focus of significant debate among scholars. It is possible that these arguments are partially explained by the type of conceptual inconsistencies that arise when publications use the same concept to convey varying levels of uncertainty between categories. Different results have been obtained from studies evaluating the relative impact of various features of uncertainty on the decision-making processes of MNCs .

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Some studies (eg . Agarwal & Ramaswami , 1992; Brouthers & Brouthers , 2003; Brouthers et al., 2008; Eroglu , 1992; Erramilli & D'Souza , 1995; Ji & Dimitratos , 2013) suggest that environmental factors are the most crucial factor. (“Uncertainty in decision-making: A review of the international business ...”) The influence of MNCs on entry mode choice, while others suggest that industry factors have the most significant impact in constraining these decisions (Cadogan et al., 2003; Elango & Sambharya , 2004; Li & Li , 2010; Sutcliffe & Zaheer , 1998). Also, comparable inconsistencies are seen within uncertainty categories when more than one concept is used to capture the same uncertainty dimension. This is because different concepts have diverse ways of being the same information.

When it comes to the unknowns surrounding the environment, inconsistencies surrounding the unknown surrounding politics and culture are most common. Political unpredictability is recognized to have a significant impact on internationalization (e.g., Henisz & Delios , 2001; Jiménez , 2010), market choice (e.g., Duanmu , 2012; Henisz & Delios , 2001) and/or divestiture. preferences of multinational companies (MNCs) (e.g., Berry , 2013). Slangen and van Tulder's (2009) research shows that studies that conceptualize environmental uncertainty in terms of political uncertainty focus on a relatively unimportant aspect of a country's formal institutional environment, concluding that government uncertainty may be a better proxy.

is even though political uncertainty being the most researched uncertainty in the IB literature . Similar debates about cultural uncertainty have been observed: Cho and Padmanabhan (2005) show the importance of cultural uncertainty in determining the type of ownership involved in MNC entry type decisions, while other studies (e.g. , Luo , 2001; Slangen & van Tulder , 2009)) indicate that cultural uncertainty is a less relevant driver of MNC decision making, or even irrelevant to it. Cho and Padmanabhan (2005) show the importance of cultural ambiguity in deciding the type of ownership involved in MNCs .

Inconsistencies in the method used to assess uncertainty can be interpreted as contributing, at least in part, to these conflicting results. For example, Slangen and van Tulder's (2009) finding that government uncertainty is a better proxy for the uncertainty of the external environment than political uncertainty can be explained by integrating different measures for similar dimensions of

uncertainty. For example, when making choices about the entry style, decision makers may only moderately consider this possibility. Moreover, although most of the studies reviewed were assessments of political uncertainty by multinational corporations, the studies evaluated political instability rather than the possible impact of politics on the organization (see Delios & Henisz , 2003a, 2003b; Henisz and Delios , 2001; Kobrin , 1979). One more example: A study conducted by Gaur , Delios , and Singh (2007) found that multinational corporations are more dependent on expatriates under conditions characterized by elevated levels of government and political instability. According to the findings of a study conducted by Xu, Pan and Beamish (2004), the opposite is true; higher levels of government and political unpredictability are linked to lower levels of equity ownership and a smaller expatriate presence. However, a more in-depth examination of these studies, Gaur et al. (2007) measure government and political uncertainties through the government and political indices of the host country, while Xu et al. (2004) focuses more on the demand forecasts of the host country and the operational efficiency of a firm. Both approaches measure the level of uncertainty associated with government and political factors.

6. Conclusion

Linguistic and religious distances have a greater impact on the behavior of multinational corporations than the more typical measures of cultural uncertainty. This is because linguistic and religious distances are indicators of cultural uncertainty (Dow et al., 2016). Some people believe that the environmental feelings of the host market are the drivers of management decision making rather than cultural distance, which has been criticized for being less important in this respect (Xu & Shenkar , 2002). Consequently, differences in the conceptualization and measurement of uncertainty are problematic as they fragment our knowledge of the subject and, more importantly, hinder the growth of our cumulative knowledge of uncertainty and its effects. Because of these inconsistencies, our understanding of the uncertainties that multinational companies prioritize when making international decisions is hampered. We have also been hampered by our understanding of how a multinational company prioritizes the uncertainties it recognizes and how this influences its decisions. Because of these differences, it is not possible for us to make a correct

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assessment of the contextual environment in which MNCs operate and choices are made (Di Gregory , 2005). In addition, the diversity of approaches used to conceptualize and quantify several types of uncertainty poses a risk to the reliability of findings obtained through empirical research and, ultimately, to the formulation of new theories (Delios & Henisz , 2003a). Considering these limitations, two main recommendations for areas of focus for future work are presented. First, to avoid further misunderstanding, it is important for researchers to choose simpler uncertainty dimensions, both conceptually and statistically, in the future. For example, Miller (1993) and Werner, Brouthers , and Brouthers (1996) recommend choosing concepts of uncertainty that are interrelated and consistent with current research on uncertainty. They supply dimensions of uncertainty that are theoretically supported and prove structure and discriminant validity. They also show construct validity. Consequently, the authors of this study suggest that similar uncertainty structures be included in future research to obtain more comprehensive measurements . Future research topics may include the following to address these methodological concerns: "What is the nature of the interaction between the various dimensions of uncertainty at the conceptual level and what constructs should be included in future scale development initiatives ?" To what extent is the grouping of various uncertainty structures generalizable across sectors and nations, and do these structures interact with each other in diverse ways? Second, since most of today's uncertainty measures are objective and derived from country reports (84 out of a total of 114 articles reviewed use country statistical indices to measure the uncertainties of MNCs), our understanding of MNC decision making must be based on the subjective reality of the uncertainties faced by real decision makers. This is because most of today's uncertainty measures are drawn from country reports. This is problematic because it does not recognize that people and teams make decisions, not the organization, and as a result it ignores a potentially broad and powerful set of explanations that could complement existing theories and models behind MNC's decision making. The problem with this is that it ignores a potentially broad and powerful set of explanations behind MNC decision-making that could complement existing theories and models.

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